

Heart Failure: Machine Learning Prediction Within a 5-year Framework

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Abstract— Heart failure (HF) is a complex syndrome that is affected by many factors and causes. It is crucial to early recognize the disease subtypes and the unidentified clinical pathways that give rise to it. Machine learning (ML) is the tool that assist to deal with these challenges and improve the prediction of HF. In this work, the HF risk prediction was done by employed ML classifiers, such as Random Forest, Extreme Grading Boosting and Light Gradient - Boosting Machine. We utilized the data from the German epidemiological trial on ankle brachial index - getABI cohort, which includes 6,000 patients approximately. The performance of classifiers was estimated by Accuracy (ACC), Sensitivity, Specificity and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) in mean values for each ML classifier. The results were also interpreted using the Explainable artificial intelligence (AI) method, the Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) plots. Our work reveals that LGBM classifier predict the HF risk within 5 years follow-up in general population with 68 % accuracy.

Keywords—heart failure, machine learning, explainable AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Heart failure (HF) is a prevalent but not commonly understood or straightforward condition within cardiovascular disease (CVD)[1]. Coronary heart disease and overbearing blood pressure are the main causes of HF. Around 63 million people are affected by HF worldwide [2]. Its prevalence is quickly increasing also, with a projected rise of 34% in the following decades [3], [4]. More than half of individuals with persistent advanced HF die within five years worldwide [5]. HF also affects around 6.7 million Americans over the age of 20, with the prevalence anticipated to increase to 8.5 million by 2030 [3].

HF risk prediction was done by enough studies. Mahmud et. al [6], proposes a ML metamodel based on clinical test data for HF prediction. The model utilized random forest, gaussian naive bayes, decision tree models, and k-nearest neighbor. The metamodel trained and tested on five datasets from Statlog Heart, Cleveland, Hungarian, Switzerland, and Long Beach, and 11 features including heart diseases, habits, and comorbidities. The proposed metamodel predicted the HF event with accuracy of 87 %. Another study [7] used the tBNA-PR model which was based on deep learning, to predict HF and recognize sub-phenotypes from electronic health records data. It achieved 78 % accuracy and 72 % AUC. This study uncovers three unique sub-phenotypes of HF patients and key aspects of each using clustering and subgroup analysis.

A study of Segar et. al. [8], analyzing four large cohort studies found that ML can offer advantages over traditional models for HF prediction after 10 years risk. The used 39 candidate variables including demographic, medical history, laboratory and electrocardiographic domains. ML models demonstrated good discrimination compared to established models or non-race-specific models. Natriuretic peptide levels were the most important predictor of HF risk across both races, followed by Troponin levels in Black population and ECG-based Cornell voltage in White population. Glycemic parameters and socioeconomic factors were also key predictors of HF risk among Black individuals. Another work of Adler et. al. [9], developed a ML algorithm to predict HF. They trained boosted decision tree algorithm on a cohort of 5822 hospitalized and ambulatory patients with HF to discriminate group of patients with low risk or high mortality risk. They also developed a risk score using this model, which is based on eight variables, such as diastolic blood pressure, creatinine, blood urea nitrogen, haemoglobin, white blood cell count, platelets,

albumin, and red blood cell distribution width. This risk score achieved 0.88 AUC demonstrating predictive power over the entire risk range. External validation in two different HF populations produced AUCs of 0.84 and 0.81, too.

We aim to predict HF based on routine clinical data, ML and Explainable AI. The getABI cohort was utilized in this analysis. The most important features according to SHAP plots were belonged to in clinical data, laboratory tests, demographics, daily habits and comorbidities. Three supervised classifiers were used for the HF prediction. LGBM was the best predictive model, outperforming the other two models and achieving the highest performance metrics. The novelty and clinical relevance of this study stands in the use of clinical routine data for the prediction of HF risk in 5 years follow-up.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Workflow

The methodology of this study is conducted in five steps, which are shown in Figure 1. At first, statistical analysis was done in the getABI cohort and then the data associated with HF were obtained from it. The following step was the feature selection, which was mainly based on SHAP plot. Moreover, the data pre-processing steps were applied on gathered data to render them suitable for further processing and analysis. The balance of classes was also done and ML classifiers were employed in the next step. The prediction of HF risk within 5 years follow-up was based on the performance of used classifiers, which was estimated by various metrics afterwards. Moreover, the XAI methods assisted to further interpretation of our results in the final step.

B. Data Description and Analysis

The analysed data was obtained from the German epidemiological trial on ankle brachial index - getABI cohort [10]. This study contains 6,454 patients being 65 years or older. Moreover, different types of data are included in this cohort, such as laboratory data, clinical tests, comorbidities, medications, and demographics. There were also a number of outcomes that were connected in various follow-ups regarding mortality events, cerebrovascular and cardiovascular diseases.

Fig. 1. Methodological steps of heart failure prediction.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF BASIC FEATURES ON GENERAL POPULATION.

Features	Mean value \pm SD / Percentage	
	Patients (852)	Control (3704)

	Mean value \pm SD / Percentage	
Age	73,9 \pm 5,3	71,6 \pm 4,8
Sex	480 females (56.3 %)	2192 females (59.2 %)
Body Mass Index (BMI)	28,06 \pm 4,48 (1 missing value)	27,18 \pm 3,93 (2 missing values)
Arterial Hypertension (AH)	620 (72.8 %)	2297 (62.0 %) 23 missing values
Diabete Mellitus (DM)	262 (30.8 %)	741 (20.0 %) 16 missing values
Dyslipidemia	497 (58.3 %) 9 Missing values	1884 (50.9 %) 53 missing values
Smoking	411 (48.2 %): Former smoker 441 (51.8 %): Non-smoker	1650 (44.5 %): Former smoker 2054 (55.5 %): Non-smoker
Myocardial infarction, baseline (first event)	128 (15.0 %)	245 (6.6 %)
Angina pectoris (confirmed), Baseline (first event)	206 (24.2 %)	414 (11.2 %)
Coronary revascularization, Baseline (first event)	101 (11.9 %)	220 (5.9 %)
Resting heart rate after 5 minutes of sitting (beats per minute)	71,61 \pm 10,45	70,98 \pm 10,06
Ankle-Brachial Index (ABI), calculated at resting baseline	1,0019 \pm 0,2080	1,0464 \pm 0,1687 5 missing values
Ankle-Brachial Index (ABI) -- calculated after loading (30 toe stands or until symptoms occur) Baseline	0,9497 \pm 0,2337	0,9918 \pm 0,1902 80 missing values
Troponin I	14,8365 \pm 106,6153 (2 missing values)	9,8901 \pm 81,84704 6 missing values
NT pro-BNP	413,1684 \pm 734,98254	205,0936 \pm 270,31599 50 missing values
Lipoprotein A	35,947 \pm 35,5187	34,650 \pm 36,5142 1 missing value
triglycerides	156,15 \pm 91,77	144,27 \pm 83,307 1 missing value
HDL cholesterol	50,34 \pm 16,58	53,33 \pm 16,48 5 missing values
LDL cholesterol	121,95 \pm 30,67	126,65 \pm 30,48 5 missing values

Our outcome was the HF event at 5 years follow-up, which includes 4,556 observations of which 852 patients were suffered from HF. The statistical analysis of basic demographic and comorbidities, laboratory data, medical history and other clinical tests at baseline are shown in Table I. Patients with HF had a mean age of 73,9 years and females were 56 %. AH affected 72.8% of individuals, whereas dyslipidaemia affected

58.3%. 411 out of 852 patients had smoked in the past. Moreover, 3704 individuals in control group had 71.6 % of mean age and 2297 were females. AH affected 62.0 % of individuals, whereas dyslipidaemia affected 50.9%. 1650 out of 3704 patients had smoked in the past.

C. Pre-processing Steps

ML-based prediction relies heavily on the data pre-processing steps. Cleaning, data transformation, missing value handling with the SimpleImputer (computing the mean values), and down-sampling for the target feature's imbalanced classes are among the approaches used.

Additionally, feature selection was initially done by hand. Specifically, the initial dataset included 557 features, which were reduced to 45 independent variables, omitting all those features with significant missing value percentage, double or similar with others, questionnaires and many endpoints at various follow-ups. Following that, the second stage of feature selection was based on the Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) algorithm. Specifically, the TreeExplainer SHAP plot based on Random Forest classifier produced the feature importance according to mean SHAP value in a plot (Fig.2). The twenty most important features, which are depicted in Fig. 2, plus sex, arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus are included in the final dataset. The last three features were considered as clinically important demographic and comorbidity data, respectively. Therefore, the final analysed dataset included 23 independent features, which belong to the following categories of data: demographics, biomarkers, daily habits, clinical data and comorbidities.

The number of patients between those with and without HF was unbalanced. Therefore, down-sampling was used to maintain the balance among the two groups. It is used to decrease bias in outcomes. All samples were retained in the minority class one, and an equal number of samples were chosen at random from the majority class zero [3]. This technique is completed when the values majority and minority class are balanced to provide an updated balanced 1:1 ratio dataset for further analysis. Moreover, the dataset was also split into 70% training and 30 % test set.

D. Machine Learning and Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Three supervised ML classifiers, such as Random Forest (RF) [11], Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [12] and Light Gradient-Boosting Machine (LGBM) [13] were applied in this analysis. Their performance was calculated by four metrics: Accuracy (ACC), Sensitivity, Specificity and Receiver Operative Characteristic Curve (ROC) and the Area under the ROC curve (AUC) were used in order to estimate the performance of each classifier. Classifiers were also employed for 100 consecutive iterations extracting mean values of metrics. SHAP plots assisted also to the interpretation of our results, shedding light on the explanation of associations between used important features of our analysis.

Fig. 2. Feature Importance according to SHAP value.

III. RESULTS

A. Classifiers performance

Our results regarding the performance of ML models and SHAP plots were extracted by Python software package. The mean values of ACC, sensitivity, specificity and AUC of each classifier are presented in Table II.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Classifiers / Metrics	Performance of classifiers		
	XGBoost (%)	Random Forest (%)	LGBM (%)
Mean AUC	62.14	64.97	67.62
Mean Accuracy	62.12	64.85	67.58
Mean Sensitivity	60.69	59.54	65.64
Mean Specificity	63.60	70.40	69.60

Our findings indicate that LGBM was the best predictive models for HF risk. It outperforms the other classifiers presenting the highest performance metrics. Especially, 68 %, 66%, 70% and 68 % were achieved by LGBM for accuracy, sensitivity, specificity and AUC, respectively. On the other hand, XGBoost presents the lowest values, achieving 62 % accuracy and AUC. Moreover, RF achieved 65 % accuracy and AUC. We also observe that the difference between values of specificity and sensitivity for each classifier is very low,

indicating that the class balance was successful, assisting to the decrease of bias.

Fig. 3. Mean receiver operating characteristic curve value for each classifier after 100 iterations.

B. Explainability of Results

The explainability of results was based on the SHAP plots. Especially, the dependence plots are depicted in Figures 4-7. We investigated the relationship between N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP), which was the most important feature according to SHAP plot (Fig. 2) and other independent variables.

Fig. 4. Dependence plot of ABI index at rest and NT-proBNP.

Specifically, NT-proBNP was plotted with ABI index before and after exercise as shown in Figures 4 and 5. The presented function “U-shaped curve” confirms that the result is right, as the ABI equal to 1.0 (normal ABI) indicates low value of NT-proBNP. We also observe that most dots at the point where the ABI is normal are blue, indicating that most patients do not have HF by having a low value of NT-proBNP. The exact same curve appears in plot of NT-proBNP with ABI index after exercise, confirming the previous observations (Fig. 5). Moreover, the plot of BMI and NT-proBNP is shown in Fig. 6, where we observe that the function is increasing. Especially, an increase in BMI has as result the increasing values of the risk factor NT-proBNP.

Fig. 5. Dependence plot of ABI index after exercise and NT-proBNP.

Fig. 6. Dependence plot of BMI and NT-proBNP.

Furthermore, Fig. 7 presents the relationship of NT-proBNP and HbA1c, proving that between the normal values of 4-6 of the glycosylated haemoglobin, the risk factor NT-proBNP decreases. We also notice that most dots-observations are in this value interval indicating the largest percentage of healthy individuals in the dataset. Conversely, increasing glycosylation rates lead to an increase in NT-proBNP as well.

Fig. 7. Dependence plot of HbA1c and NT-proBNP.

IV. DISCUSSION

The prediction of HF risk was achieved by LGBM with 68 % of accuracy. We used 23 features, which can be easily collected in daily clinical routine. Our work shed light on the interpretation of results, explaining the associations between significant features. Shapley plots were used to identify essential features that contributed the most to HF prediction. The five most important features are NT-proBNP, age, ABI index at rest, BMI, and Troponin I, which presented the highest SHAP values, indicating their substantial impact on the model's predictions.

The most important feature of our analysis, NT-proBNP, is in accordance with current literature and professional standards, indicating the reliability of our analysis. Specifically, NT-proBNP is frequently measured serially in clinical practice. Increased concentration of NT-proBNP occurs well in advance of event commencement, and repeated assessments are a robust predictor of outcomes in heart failure with lower ejection fraction [14], [15]. Moreover, early and more accurate diagnosis can result from knowledge of and application of NT-proBNP levels [16]. These results may support routine NT-proBNP monitoring to assist in clinical decision making.

However, there are some limitations in our analysis, including the dataset, which contained a low number of individuals. Moreover, there is a need to application of more ML models. The presented models, particularly LGBM, remain complex. It will be useful to reduce their complexity and simply them without sacrificing performance, in order to be more practical for use in clinical settings.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on the HF risk prediction within 5 years follow-up and identification of the most important features. The getABI cohort comprised of 4,556 patients, of which 852 patients with HF. XGBoost, random forest and LGBM seek to predict HF. LGBM outperformed the others classifiers, achieving the highest average metrics (68 % accuracy) after 100 consecutive iterations. The use of XAI method, SHAP plots provided valuable insights into the feature importance and interpretability of our results. We also used 23 clinical routine data which enhance the prediction. The primary findings emphasize the crucial role of variables including age, NT-proBNP, BMI, ABI index at rest, and Troponin I in predicting HF risk. These features make our model easier to apply in ordinary clinical practice since they are useful for routine clinical collection in addition to being important for prediction. We now have a better knowledge of the underlying risk factors for HF due to SHAP plots, which further highlighted significant correlations and interactions across features. The novel aspect of this work is produced by the combination of the usage of NT-proBNP as an indirect marker of HF and the prediction of such a misunderstood syndrome.

Despite the promising results, our work presents some drawbacks, including the requirement for external validation, the limited population size, and the low number of applied ML models. Overall, the combination of ML models with SHAP

analysis provides a strong approach to predicting HF, with practical findings that can enhance early identification and patient treatment.

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